

Biosorption of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* from multimetal solution

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Biosorption of cadmium by a cadmium tolerant variant of *Aspergillus niger* in presence of lead, nickel and chromium from synthetic aqueous culture medium has been studied. *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ absorbed 98.2% cadmium from culture medium containing 2 µg/ml cadmium under optimized physical and chemical parameters. More than 90% of cadmium was absorbed by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ from culture medium containing other toxic heavy metals. Cadmium biosorption capacity decreased sharply when lead, nickel and chromium were added at a time at a concentration over 5.0 µg/ml, 2.5 µg/ml and 5.0 µg/ml respectively and over 5.0 µg/ml when added in combination.

Cadmium concentration in the polluted water has dramatically accelerated since the beginning of the industrial revolution¹. Cadmium metal compounds are used mainly in electroplating industries, metal-finishing industries, battery manufacturing industries etc. Concentration of this hazardous substance has to be decreased to permissible levels by appropriate treatment methods. Conventional chemical treatment methods, such as precipitation-filtration, oxidation-reduction, ion exchange, electrochemical recovery, membrane separation and other techniques, may be ineffective or uneconomical when the cadmium concentration in the polluted water is in the range of 10 to 100 µg/ml and the permissible concentration is less than 1 mg/L². In this connection microbial uptake of cadmium could be much more economical than chemical treatment processes. Many microorganisms including bacteria^{3,4}, algae^{5,6}, fungi⁷⁻¹¹ and yeasts^{9,12,13} concentrate heavy metals at different capacities. Fungi and yeasts are considered to be more effective especially because of their high cell wall binding capacity. Metal uptake in fungi and yeasts are known to involve an initial rapid binding of metals to negatively charged sites on the cell wall (biosorption) followed by a slower, energy dependent entry inside the cell¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

Aspergillus niger, dead or alive, used extensively to remove metals¹¹ from metal bearing waste water due to its ease of culturing and lack of pathogenicity to humans and animals¹⁷. A cadmium tolerant strain, *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ has been isolated in our laboratory which absorbed greater percentage of cadmium than other metals. The object of this study is to determine the possibility of environmental application of *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ for treatment of cadmium contaminated water in the presence of other heavy metals such as nickel, lead and chromium.

Results and discussion

A variant of filamentous fungal species, *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀, has been reported earlier¹⁸ to remove maximum amount of cadmium from cadmium containing synthetic growth medium. The uptake of cadmium is greater than the other metals (viz. lead, nickel and chromium) when single metal is used at a time in the synthetic growth medium. Table 1 shows the extent of biosorption of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ from synthetic culture media

Table 1. Removal of cadmium from culture medium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀

Concentration of the culture medium µg/ml	Removal of cadmium from culture medium % Mean ± S.E.	Removal of cadmium from culture medium µg/g dry cell mass Mean ± S.E.
0.5	97.5 ± 0.30	27.33 ± 0.77
1.0	98.5 ± 0.13	65.41 ± 0.71
1.5	97.9 ± 0.35	99.36 ± 0.99
2.0	98.2 ± 0.16	135.45 ± 1.29
2.5	93.5 ± 0.33	165.78 ± 1.08
3.0	82.3 ± 0.16	189.34 ± 0.87
3.5	72.3 ± 0.34	236.50 ± 1.07
4.0	55.6 ± 0.24	230.23 ± 0.65

containing different concentrations of cadmium under optimum physical conditions¹⁹ and chemical composition²⁰. It is observed from Table 1 that the increase in the percentage of biosorption of cadmium is negligible (97.5 to 98.5%) up to 2 µg/ml cadmium concentration in the medium. The percentage of biosorption of cadmium decreases when the concentration of cadmium in the medium is greater than 2.0 µg/ml. This can be explained by the fact that cadmium

gradually becomes toxic to the strain as the concentration increases. But the biosorption of cadmium in terms of amount of cadmium per g of cellular dry weight is increased (236.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry mass) up to a cadmium concentration of 3.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. This may be due to the fact that when metal cation binding sites on the cell wall are mostly occupied, then metal ions begin to move inside the cell²¹. Although the total cell mass decreases at higher cadmium concentration (toxicity effect), the cadmium binding sites might be mostly occupied due to greater availability of cadmium at that concentration and considerable amount of cadmium might be taken up internally which has resulted in the increased amount of cadmium in the cell biomass with increasing initial concentration of cadmium in the medium.

One emerging field of study is the biosorption of a metal from multimetal solutions. In the present study, biosorption of cadmium in presence of some heavy metals has also been monitored. Table 2 shows the extent of biosorption of

cadmium as well as nickel, lead and chromium in presence of different concentrations of the three metals separately with a fixed concentration of cadmium (2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the medium. Cadmium biosorption decreases in presence of other metals at higher concentration. But the decrease has been found to be different for different metal. In presence of 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 2.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ nickel concentration, the decrease of cadmium biosorption is not very appreciable (98.2 to 95.2%). But when nickel concentration is higher than 2.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the cadmium biosorption decreases considerably to 90.7% although the amount of cadmium biosorption (in $\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry weight) increases from 135.45 to 187.65 $\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry weight due to decrease in cellular growth and maximum binding of cadmium to the cell wall binding sites.

Lead has prominent effect on the biosorption of cadmium due to the toxicity on the organism. The percentage biosorption of cadmium remains virtually unaffected in the presence of lead up to the concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (97.5%).

Table 2. Removal of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ from synthetic culture medium in presence of nickel, lead and chromium in individual experiments

Concentration of cadmium in the culture medium in all the experiments was 2 mg/ml

Concentration of nickel in the culture medium $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Removal of cadmium from culture medium % Mean \pm S.E	Removal of cadmium from culture medium $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry cell mass Mean \pm S.E	Removal of the other metal from culture medium % Mean \pm S.E	Removal of the other metal from culture medium $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry cell mass Mean \pm S.E
0.0	98.20 \pm 0.16	135.45 \pm 1.29	00.00 \pm 0.00	00.00 \pm 0.00
1.0	97.20 \pm 0.30	136.36 \pm 0.79	70.50 \pm 0.29	49.30 \pm 1.20
2.5	95.20 \pm 0.18	135.80 \pm 1.21	62.70 \pm 0.39	111.80 \pm 1.21
5.0	90.70 \pm 0.21	150.66 \pm 1.90	30.60 \pm 0.24	127.08 \pm 0.99
7.5	80.50 \pm 0.24	187.65 \pm 1.20	15.25 \pm 0.33	133.30 \pm 0.86
Concentration of lead in the culture medium $\mu\text{g/ml}$				
0.0	98.20 \pm 0.16	135.45 \pm 1.29	00.00 \pm 0.00	00.00 \pm 0.00
1.0	97.50 \pm 0.26	138.30 \pm 1.05	42.30 \pm 0.34	30.14 \pm 1.38
2.5	92.60 \pm 0.30	146.52 \pm 0.87	29.20 \pm 0.39	57.75 \pm 1.03
5.0	79.20 \pm 0.31	160.32 \pm 1.16	15.30 \pm 0.18	80.66 \pm 1.66
7.5	51.50 \pm 0.29	179.85 \pm 1.47	10.10 \pm 0.16	92.93 \pm 0.82
Concentration of chromium in the culture medium $\mu\text{g/ml}$				
0.0	98.20 \pm 0.16	135.45 \pm 1.29	00.00 \pm 0.00	00.00 \pm 0.00
1.0	95.50 \pm 0.30	133.45 \pm 1.14	68.20 \pm 0.19	47.30 \pm 0.66
2.5	93.70 \pm 0.36	132.34 \pm 1.02	53.50 \pm 0.27	94.46 \pm 0.77
5.0	91.50 \pm 0.30	130.84 \pm 0.83	31.10 \pm 0.20	111.47 \pm 0.95
7.5	82.50 \pm 0.31	132.20 \pm 0.53	22.30 \pm 0.27	123.80 \pm 0.81

Table 3. Removal of cadmium in presence of nickel, lead and chromium together from culture medium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀. Concentration of cadmium in the culture medium in all the experiments were 2 µg/ml

Concentration of nickel, lead and chromium in the culture medium (µg/ml)	Removal of metals from culture medium % (Mean ±S.E)				Removal of metals from culture medium µg/g dry cell biomass (Mean ±S.E)			
	Cd	Ni	Pb	Cr	Cd	Ni	Pb	Cr
0	98.2 ± 0.16	00.0 ± 0.00	00.0 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	135.45 ± 1.29	00.00 ± 0.00	00.00 ± 0.00	00.00 ± 0.00
1	94.5 ± 0.20	61.3 ± 0.22	35.5 ± 0.27	65.3 ± 0.28	134.04 ± 1.09	43.48 ± 0.87	25.18 ± 0.68	46.31 ± 0.64
2.5	91.2 ± 0.14	42.6 ± 0.24	18.6 ± 0.41	45.7 ± 0.46	128.35 ± 0.65	76.62 ± 0.51	33.45 ± 1.20	82.19 ± 0.81
5	75.6 ± 0.35	15.6 ± 0.39	10.3 ± 0.31	18.3 ± 0.39	144.00 ± 1.40	74.29 ± 1.16	49.05 ± 0.81	87.14 ± 0.43
7.5	43.7 ± 0.42	10.2 ± 0.21	9.3 ± 0.28	12.8 ± 0.27	143.28 ± 1.06	125.41 ± 0.96	114.34 ± 0.95	127.38 ± 0.54

At higher concentration of lead, decrease of biosorption of cadmium is prominent (97.5 to 51.5% at a concentration of lead 7.5 µg/ml) due to the decrease of growth of the organism as lead is more toxic than cadmium. Cadmium and lead removal in terms of µg/g dry biomass still increase with increasing lead concentration in the medium. The maximum cadmium removal has been observed 179.85 µg/g dry biomass when 7.5 µg/ml lead is present in the medium although the growth of the organism is very poor (results not shown).

Chromium, when present in the medium exerted little effect (98.2 to 91.5%) on the biosorption of cadmium by the organism up to the concentration of 5 µg/ml. At higher concentration of chromium (7.5 µg/ml), cadmium biosorption decreases from 91.5 to 82.5% with decreasing cellular growth. Cadmium removal in terms of µg/g dry biomass remains constant (135.45–130.34 µg/g dry biomass) at all concentrations of chromium in that case.

Cadmium biosorption in terms of percentage of removal and µg/g dry biomass is observed in presence of nickel, lead and chromium altogether in combination at different concentrations (1–7.5 µg/ml). Biosorption of three metals are also observed. The results are shown in Table 3. Cadmium biosorption is virtually unaffected (94.5 to 91.2%) in presence of nickel, lead and chromium in combination up to the concentration of 2.5 µg/ml in the medium. At higher concentration of the above metals, cadmium biosorption decreases sharply (75.6% at 5 µg/ml to 43.7% at 7.5 µg/ml). The extent of cadmium biosorption in terms of µg/g dry biomass is not very appreciable (from 128.35 to 144.0 µg/g), might be due to the combined effect of decrease of cellular growth and increase in internalization of the metal. Biosorption of nickel, lead and chromium decrease sharply in terms of percentage of removal and in µg/g dry biomass with increase in their concentration in comparison to cadmium. This might be due to some specificity towards cad-

mium binding by the strain *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ as the strain is developed by adapting it in high concentration of cadmium¹⁸.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the study were of A.R. grade (E. Merck) and the media preparation and volume make up were done by double-distilled water.

Aspergillus niger AB₁₀, a cadmium tolerant strain¹⁸ was used in this study. The microorganism was subcultured to maintain in Czapek-Dox agar slants and stored at 4°.

Spore suspension was prepared as described by Bandopadhyay and Banik²². Six days old culture of *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ was used for the preparation of spore suspension. The concentration of the spores was adjusted to 2×10^5 spores/ml in all the experiments.

Composition of synthetic culture medium²⁰ for metal uptake experiments was (as g/100 ml); sucrose-6, NH₄NO₃-0.2, KH₂PO₄-0.1, KCl-0.02, MgSO₄·7H₂O-0.01, FeSO₄·7H₂O-0.005. pH of the medium was adjusted to 4.5. Systronic-335 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. Stock solutions of Cd(NO₃)₂, Pb(NO₃)₂, NiSO₄ and K₂Cr₂O₇ having concentration of 1000 µg/ml with respect to the metals were prepared separately. Calculated volumes of these solutions were added to the synthetic growth medium to achieve the desired metal concentrations (viz. 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 5.0, 7.5 µg/ml) for the metal uptake studies. 50 ml of synthetic culture medium was taken in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks containing desired metal concentration. Freshly prepared spore suspension was added (2×10^5 spores/ml of the growth medium) to the medium and incubated at 28° for 8 days¹⁹. All the experiments were done in quadruplicate sets and mean results with standard errors calculated as per standard formula, had been mentioned.

After desired period of incubation, the cell mass were separated by filtration, washed thoroughly with double-distilled water and digested with 6 N HNO₃²³. The metal concentrations in the digests were analysed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model : Varian, SP20BQ) after proper dilution²⁴.

Cellular growth was determined by the method of Norris and Kelly²⁵.

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